

Stability and Thermodynamics of Salicylamide Complexes with Hg(II), Ce(III) and La(III)

B. S. PANNU, B. S. SEKHON & S. L. CHOPRA

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, (India)

Manuscript received 21 May 1973; accepted 4 July 1973

THE equilibrium study of the metal complexes of phenolic and related compounds as ligands has recently come more and more into the foreground of interest. In this connection, the complex forming properties of salicylamide have also been investigated. Agren¹ has determined the complexity constants between iron (III) and salicylamide. Chakraburty *et al.*² have reported the formation of a complex of salicylamide with uranyl ion which was used for the colorimetric determination. The stability constants of salicylamide with Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Mg(II) were determined by Jabalpurwala and co-workers³. The stabilities of salicylamide complexes of Mg(II), Be(II) and Al(III) have also been studied by Das and Rao⁴. In this paper the stability constants and some thermodynamic functions of the complexes of salicylamide with Hg(II) and Ce(III) and La(III) have been reported.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Salicylamide was recrystallized from aqueous ethanol (m.p. found 140°). Carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared by the standard method⁵. Dioxan was purified by the method of Riddick and Toops⁶. Standard solution of this reagent was prepared by dissolving it in pure dioxan. The solutions of Hg(II), Ce(III) and La(III) salts were prepared in double distilled deionized water. The pH-titrations were carried out in 50% dioxan-water medium. Solutions of potassium nitrate and nitric acid were used to maintain the ionic strength at 0.3M. Potassium hydroxide (0.1M) was used for titrations. pH measurements were made using a Systronic pH meter with glass and calomel electrode assembly. The pH readings were accurate within ± 0.05 . The thermostatic bath temperatures were maintained at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

For each set of experiments, three titrations were carried out adopting Irving-Rossotti method⁷. Solutions containing: (1) free mineral acid (0.01M); (2) free mineral acid + ligand (0.05M); (3) free mineral acid + ligand + metal ion (0.01 M) were titrated with a standard solution of potassium hydroxide. The initial volume of the solution was 40 ml. The plots of pH of the solutions against the volume of the alkali added were drawn. The shapes of the titration curves were as usual.

The proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1$) and the \bar{n} -pL data pairs corresponding to the formation curves were calculated from the pH metric titration data in the usual way⁷. The stability constants were obtained from the formation curves

applying the correction term method of Irving and Rossotti⁸.

Results and Discussion

The formation curves of Hg(II), Ce(III) and La(III) complexes at 30° may be seen in Fig. 1. The \bar{n} values for complexes of all systems show that they are greater than 1 and less than 2, indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The values of protonation constants of salicylamide are 9.56 and 9.50 at 30° and 40° respectively. The values of the successive formation constants for various systems are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SALICYLAMIDE COMPLEXES

Metal ion	T = 30°			T = 40°		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
Hg(II)	4.61	3.75	8.36	6.14	4.37	10.51
Ce(III)	5.68	4.75	10.43	7.20	5.38	12.58
La(III)	4.23	3.23	7.46	4.71	3.48	8.19

The following relationships were used to derive the thermodynamic parameters.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

$$\frac{d \ln K}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2}$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S.$$

The values of free energy of formation (ΔG) enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) are summarized in Table 2 to 4.

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGY DATA OF METAL SALICYLAMIDE COMPLEXES IN KCAL/MOLE

Metal ion	T(°C)	-ΔG ₁	-ΔG ₂	-ΔG
Hg(II)	30	6.4	5.2	11.6
	40	8.8	6.3	15.1
Ce(III)	30	7.9	6.6	14.5
	40	10.3	7.7	18.0
La(III)	30	5.9	4.5	10.4
	40	6.7	5.1	11.8

From Table 1, the order of stability is Ce(III) > Hg(II) > La(III) which is justified on the basis of ratio of effective nuclear charge to the ionic radii of the metal ions. For trivalent metal ions, the stability order is Ce(III) > La(III). This order of stability follows from the fact that the stability increases with the increase in atomic number of the metal.

FIG. 1. METAL LIGAND FORMATION CURVES
Formation curves for metal-ligand complexes

Fig. 2

TABLE 3—ENTHALPY DATA OF METAL SALICYLAMIDE COMPLEXES IN KCAL/MOLE

Metal ion	ΔH_1	ΔH_2	ΔH
Hg(II)	66.4	26.9	93.3
Ce(III)	65.9	27.3	93.2
La(III)	20.8	15.2	36.0

$\Delta H = \Delta H_1 + \Delta H_2$ calculated from stability constants at 30° and 40°.

TABLE 4—ENTROPY DATA OF METAL-SALICYLAMIDE COMPLEXES AT 30° IN CAL/DEG/MOLE

Metal ion	ΔS_1	ΔS_2	ΔS
Hg(II)	240.2	105.9	346.1
Ce(III)	243.6	111.9	355.5
La(III)	88.1	64.9	153.0

The values of $\log K_1/K_2$ are positive in all cases (Table 1). The values of $\log \beta_2$ at 40° are greater than the values of $\log \beta_2$ at 30° which show that higher temperature is favourable for the formation of complexes and their stabilities are enhanced. The

free energies of formation of these chelates have high negative values at 40° and less at 30° and this points to their spontaneous formation (Table 2). It is further seen that the values of ΔH are positive in all the three cases (Table 3) so that the reactions of salicylamide with the metal ions occur with the absorption of energy. The results in Table 4 show that in all systems, entropy changes (ΔS) accompanying the formation of complexes are positive. As a result of this the entropy term (ΔS) strongly favours the complex formation and accordingly chelation effect is essentially an entropy effect. The high value of the entropy changes have probably resulted from greater disruption of water structure surrounding the metal ion and resulting in the formation of chelates. The very large entropy changes (ΔS) is also justified by considering the greater availability of co-ordination sites on these metal ions.

The complexes formed with salicylamide can be represented by structural formula I and II for divalent metal ions and trivalent metal ions respectively.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (B.S.P. and B.S.S.) thank the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. A. AGREN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 39.
2. A. K. CHAKRABURTY, D. SEN and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 30, 491.

3. K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. A. VENKATACHALAN and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1027.
4. P. CHARAN DAS and G. S. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 547.
5. A. I. VOGEL, *A text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, Longmans Green, London, 1961.
6. J. A. RIDDICK and E. E. TOOPS, JR. *Organic Solvents*, 2nd Ed., John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1954.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.

Manganese(III) Complexes of Schiff Bases

K. DEY* & K. C. RAY

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal

Manuscript received 4 June 1973; accepted 24 July 1973

RECENTLY we have used various Schiff bases of salicylaldehyde, substituted salicylaldehydes and acetylacetone with different diamines to synthesise metal chelates of iron(III)¹, cobalt(III)^{2,3,4}, chromium(III)², and manganese(III)^{2,5}. We have now isolated some manganese(III) complexes of the dibasic tetradentate Schiff base derived from orthohydroxyacetophenone and ethylenediamine (abbreviated as HAEN-H₂), the preparation and properties of which are described in this note.

Experimental

Manganese(III) acetate dihydrate was prepared by a previously published method⁶. All the solvents and chemicals were purified and dried by standard methods, the molar conductance, electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibilities were measured and elemental analyses were performed as described previously². Infrared spectra (KBr) were obtained through the commercial service from Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

Preparation of the Mn(III)-Schiff base complexes :

Mn(HAEN)(CH₃COO)(H₂O) : An ethanolic solution (20 ml.) of the Schiff base, HAEN-H₂ (0.02 mole) was added to manganese(III) acetate dihydrate (0.02 mole) dissolved in hot ethanol (20 ml), and the mixture was refluxed on water-bath for about an hour. The volume of the mixture was then reduced to half and cooled when dark brown crystals separated out. The crystals were filtered off, washed thoroughly with a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1, v/v) and dried in a vacuum desiccator. (Found : Mn, 14.00; N, 7.04%; calc. for Mn(HAEN)(CH₃COO)(H₂O) : Mn, 13.85; N, 6.60%; μ_{eff} = 4.87 B.M. (24°); Λ_M = 10.02 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ (Conc. 1.1 × 10⁻³ M in acetonitrile); ν_{max} at 25,000 cm⁻¹ (log ϵ = 3.56) and at 20,850 cm⁻¹ (log ϵ = 2.89) (in methanol); ν_{as} COO at 1540 cm⁻¹ and ν_{sym} COO at 1420 cm⁻¹; $\nu_{C=N}$ at 1595 cm⁻¹; ν_{C-O} (phenolic) at 1310 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_{C=N}$ at 1605 cm⁻¹ and ν_{C-O} (phenolic) at 1285 cm⁻¹ for free Schiff base HAEN-H₂).

Mn(HAEN)X (where, X = Cl, Br, I) : The compounds were prepared by the addition of the appropriate lithium halides to a refluxing (1-2 hr) mixture of manganese(III) acetate dihydrate and the Schiff base (all in equimolar quantities). The coloured complexes separated out on slow cooling, were washed and dried as before.

Mn(HAEN)Cl : Brown (Found : Mn, 14.62; N, 7.39; Cl, 9.00%; calc. for Mn(HAEN)Cl : Mn, 14.29; N, 7.28; Cl, 9.20%; μ_{eff} = 4.88 B.M. (at 24°); Λ_M = 12.5 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ (Conc. 1.5 × 10⁻³ M in acetonitrile); ν_{max} at 24,890 cm⁻¹ (log ϵ = 3.59) and at 20,958 cm⁻¹ (log ϵ = 2.99) (in methanol).

Mn(HAEN)Br : Brown (Found : Mn, 13.21; N, 6.40; Br, 18.90%; calc. for Mn(HAEN)Br : Mn, 12.81; N, 6.53; Br, 18.65%; μ_{eff} = 4.7 B.M. (at 23°); Λ_M = 9.8 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ (Conc. 1.0 × 10⁻³ M in acetonitrile); ν_{max} at 24,900 cm⁻¹ (log ϵ = 3.60) and at 20,000 (log ϵ = 3.00) (in methanol).

Mn(HAEN)I : Reddish-brown (Found : Mn, 11.67; N, 6.02; I, 27.01%; calc. for Mn(HAEN)I : Mn, 11.54; N, 5.88; I, 26.68%; μ_{eff} = 4.90 B.M. (at 24); Λ_M = 15.8 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ (Conc. 1.1 × 10⁻³ M in acetonitrile); ν_{max} at 24,780 cm⁻¹ (log ϵ = 3.52) and at 20,900 cm⁻¹ (log ϵ = 2.88) (in methanol).

Results and Discussion

The complexes are all coloured and quite stable when dried. The elemental analyses correspond to the formulae shown for the complexes under investigation and are all paramagnetic with effective magnetic moments in the range 4.70-4.90 B.M., which is fairly close to the spin-only value for high-spin d⁴ system. They are moderately soluble in methanol, acetonitrile and nitromethane and are practically non-conducting in acetonitrile. The molar conductance values support the coordination of the anions (i.e., CH₃COO, Cl, Br, and I). The IR spectrum of Mn(HAEN)(CH₃COO)(H₂O) has been measured in KBr phase, and ν_{as} COO and ν_{sym} COO bands are observed at 1540 cm⁻¹ and 1420 cm⁻¹ respectively, and the difference between these two bands is 120 cm⁻¹ indicating (possibly) the unidentate nature of acetate ion⁷. The ν_{as} COO band has been shifted to lower frequency compared with other unidentate acetate ion⁷. This is considered to be a consequence of hydrogen bonding by the acetate ion, the structure having strong intramolecular hydrogen-bonding between the non-coordinated carboxy-oxygen atoms and a water molecule as well as intermolecular hydrogen-bonding between each of the carboxy-oxygen atoms and water molecules coordinated to other Mn(III) ion. The $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{C-O} (phenolic) are observed at 1605 cm⁻¹ and 1285 cm⁻¹ respectively in the free ligand, which have been shifted to 1595 cm⁻¹ and 1310 cm⁻¹ respectively in the complex. The lowering of the C = N stretching frequency is an indication of the coordination of imine-nitrogen atom and thus indicating the less double bond character in the C = N bond⁸. The shift of phenolic C-O to higher frequency in the complex is possibly due to the change of hydrogen bonded structure to covalent metal bonded structure⁹.